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ТЕОРИИ ПРОИСХОЖДЕНИЯ ЯЗЫКА

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THEORIES ON THE ORIGIN OF LANGUAGE

Аннотация.

Еще в глубокой древности люди интересовались вопросом о происхождении языка. Он до сих пор остается одним из наиболее сложных и до конца не решенных в языкознании. Языки, существующие сегодня на земле, находятся уже на высоком уровне развития. Происхождение же языка относится к эпохе с архаичными формами взаимоотношений людей. Поэтому все теории происхождения языка являются гипотетическими.

Было создано много теорий, пытающихся объяснить, как же люди создали язык, что послужило причиной его возникновения. В итоге сейчас существует более 500 различных теорий происхождения языка.

Abstract.

Even in ancient times, people were interested in the question of the origin of language. It still remains one of the most complex and not fully resolved in linguistics. The languages that exist on earth today are already at a high level of development. The origin of language dates back to an era with archaic forms of human relationships. Therefore, all theories of the origin of language are hypothetical.

Many theories have been created trying to explain how people created the language, what caused its emergence. As a result, there are now more than 500 different theories of the origin of language.

Ключевые слова: происхождение языка, мифологическая теория, биологические теории, звукоподражательная теория, теория междометий

Keywords: origin of language, mythological theory, biological theories, onomatopoeic theory, interjection theory

The question of the origin of language has worried mankind since ancient times. Scientists of Ancient Greece, China, India, Egypt tried to solve it. This problem was solved in subsequent centuries. However, complete clarity has not yet been achieved. Why? Because the only witness to this process is the language itself, but it has already changed so much that it is possible to reconstruct its "childhood" only hypothetically.

There is no doubt that the question of the origin of language is inextricably linked with the question of the origin of man and human society.

The ancient mythological theory of the origin of language (language is given to man by God) is opposed by scientific theories that try to explain the emergence of various kinds of language by natural, material causes.

Among the conditions under which language developed were factors associated with the evolution of the human organism, and factors associated with the transformation of the human primitive herd into society. Therefore, all existing scientific hypotheses about the origin of the language (according to those features that are recognized as determining in its emergence and development) can be divided into two main groups - biological and social.

Biological theories of the origin of language

Biological theories explain the origin of language by the evolution of the human body - the sense organs, the speech apparatus and the brain. Positive in these theories is that they consider the emergence of language as the result of a long development of nature, thereby rejecting the simultaneous (divine) origin of language. The most famous among biological hypotheses are onomatopoeic and interjection.

The onomatopoeic theory explains the origin of language by the evolution of hearing organs that perceive natural noises. According to this point of view, language appeared due to the fact that a person learned to repeat the sounds that he heard around him. Until the 19th century, many scientists believed that all words arose from the unconscious desire of ancient man to imitate the sound of the wind, the splashing and murmur of water, the cries of animals. At first glance, this theory may appear to be correct. Indeed, in all languages there are onomatopoeic words, for example: wow-wow, cuckoo, ding, bang, and so on. Moreover, onomatopoeia could become a source of formation of meaningful words: bark, cuckoo, crow, meow. [1]

But if this theory were true, then people all over the globe would have to call some simple things the

same, or at least similar. So, it seems that sneezing in different languages should be represented by the same sounds. In fact, in some languages (related to each other) these words are similar to each other, while in others they are completely different. Here are some examples: English - Atchu, Spanish - Atchis, German - Hatshi, Russian - Apchi, French - Atshuen. This is in related languages. And in Japanese - goo-goo, in Indonesia - wahing. This means that onomatopoeic words receive sound design in accordance with the prevailing phonetic structure of a particular language. In addition, there are relatively few onomatopoeic words in languages. Therefore, this theory is unable to explain the origin of language.[5]

The interjection theory is that the first words were involuntary cries, interjections associated with the expression of human emotions caused by pain, hunger, fear, joy. Here is how the American linguist Franklin Folsom expressively writes about this: "Wow!" - perhaps, this is how a prehistoric hunter once exclaimed, throwing down a deer, which he dragged to the camp. And his family members may have begun to repeat this sound every time after hard work. "Wow!" - so, perhaps, the hunter's daughter said, seeing what a big deer her father had brought. "Ugh!" - perhaps the hunter's wife exhaled this sound, butchering a deer with a not too sharp stone for lack of a knife. "Ai!" - could have escaped from her little son when he snatched a piece of hot meat straight from the fire and burned himself. Consequently, the supporters of this theory believed that a person conveyed his feelings with interjections, which were fixed in a certain situation and, in the course of further development, became the same for all members of this community, turning into words. However, most of the words of the language, naming objects and phenomena, have nothing to do with interjections.

Social theories of the origin of language

These theories explain the emergence of language by social needs that arose in the process of labor and as a result of the development of human consciousness. Social theories of language development include the theory of the social contract and the theory of labor cries. In the theory of the social contract, first proposed by the ancient philosopher Diodorus Siculus and widely adopted in the 18th century, language is seen as a conscious invention of people at a certain stage in the development of human society: people invented language when they needed it. But after all, in order to agree on something, it would be necessary to already have some means of communication, that is, language. Therefore, this theory cannot explain the origin of language. The formation of the language could be carried out only gradually.[2]

In the late seventies of the nineteenth century, the philosopher L. Noiret put forward the so-called labor theory of the origin of the language, or the theory of labor cries. He rightly emphasized that when working together, cries and exclamations facilitate and organize labor activity. "When women are spinning and soldiers are marching," wrote Noiret, "they like to accompany their work with more or less rhythmic exclamations. These cries, at first involuntary, gradually turned into symbols of labor processes. Originally, language was a collection of verbal roots." This theory, in fact, is a variant of the interjection theory. In the process of joint

activity, such cries apparently took place, but it is unlikely that language as a whole developed from sounds that have an instinctive character.[3]

The labor theory of the origin of language was further developed in the work of F. Engels "Dialectics of Nature" in the chapter "The role of labor in the process of turning a monkey into a man." In this work, the emergence of language is presented as a very long and very complex process caused by a number of reasons. F. Engels connects the emergence of both man and language with the labor process. "The development of labor," he writes, "necessarily contributed to a closer unity of the members of society, since thanks to it, cases of mutual support, joint activity for each individual member became frequent. In short, people who were being formed came to the point that they had a need to say something to each other. Need created its own organ: the undeveloped larynx of the monkey was slowly but steadily transformed by modulation for more and more developed modulation, and the organs of the mouth gradually learned to pronounce one articulate sound after another. And further: "First work, and then articulate speech along with it, were the two most important stimuli, under the influence of which the brain of a monkey gradually turned into a human brain, which, for all its resemblance to a monkey, far exceeds it in size and perfection."

F. Engels emphasizes that the question of the origin of language is inseparable from the question of the origin of man. Therefore, to solve this problem, it is necessary to involve the data of such sciences as ethnography, anthropology, archeology, paleontology and general history, which is reflected in the biosocial theory of the origin of the language.

The study of the communication systems of animals in general and great apes in particular allowed scientists in the last decades of the twentieth century to come to an understanding of the natural origin of human language from the communication systems of great apes. [4]. Modern primates have up to 300 verbal and non-verbal cues that they use effectively in everyday interactions with each other. In the process of evolution of the great ape, this system did not disappear, but improved, since the development of the human brain as a result of labor required the complication of the forms of interaction between human individuals, which stimulated a quantitative increase in signals and their specialization. In the speech of a primitive man there were interjections, and onomatopoeia, and labor cries - all these elements subsequently entered the developing and improving human language and became its components. The modern language of mankind is a system of communicative signals of primitive people, inherited from their monkey ancestors and improved in the process of evolution.

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